

Dendrochronological analysis of diverse timbers from Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, Germany

Aoife Daly

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Seventy samples from a range of timbers from Mecklenbug-Vorpommern, Germany, were submitted for dendrochronological analysis, to determine their date and to contribute to chronology building for the region. The results of these analyses are described in this report.

As proposed 30 November 2021 (dendro.dk invoice no. 2021 R043), 40 samples from the dendrochronological sample archive of Landesamt für Kultur und Denkmalpflege Mecklenburg-Vorpommern - Landesarchäologie were to be measured and dated, with a view to securing the dataset, so that it can be utilised for future dendrochronological research. For practicality, this batch included samples from a range of ship timbers. A total of 48 samples have been analysed. In this report an expanded description of the dating and provenance determination results are presented.

The majority of the samples are oak (*Quercus* sp.). Just two samples are not oak, one of these is pine (*Pinus* sp.) and the second is probably alder (*Alnus* sp.) (see catalogue below).

	PCH5154449	PCH515521a	PCH5155239	PCH5155249	PCH515440a	PCH5155259	PCH5155269
PCH5154449	*	7.01	5.11	5.17	5.23	2.8	3.47
PCH515521a	7.01	*	6.28	5.14	6.1	4.17	5.82
PCH5155239	5.11	6.28	*	16.6	6.41	5.51	7.47
PCH5155249	5.17	5.14	16.6	*	5.44	3.92	5.62
PCH515440a	5.23	6.1	6.41	5.44	*	7.85	10.1
PCH5155259	2.8	4.17	5.51	3.92	7.85	*	16.6
PCH5155269	3.47	5.82	7.47	5.62	10.1	16.6	*

Table 1 Friedrichsruhe Fpl 2. Result of the correlation (*r*-value) of each dated oak tree-ring curve against each other.

Friedrichsruhe

Twelve samples are from Friedrichsruhe Fpl 2. Four samples contain less than 60 rings, and these are not analysed further. Of the eight samples that are analysed dendrochronologically, seven are dated. One of these dated samples has sapwood preserved. It is from a tree felled c. AD 850-865. The structure that these samples come from are felled in the mid-9th century AD (see fig. 1).

The dated samples present a very homogeneous group (table 1) and an average of all seven is made. The correlations that this average achieves against northern European tree-ring datasets is shown in table 2. The average is correlating significantly with a range of tree-ring datasets, both master and site chronologies, for oak across Northern Europe. The highest t -values are with Lübeck, Schleswig-Holstein and southern Sweden. The timbers for the structures at Friedrichsruhe Fpl 2 were probably attained locally.

Filename	start year-end year	PCH515M02 Friedrichsruhe AD568-AD845	site name
Master chronologies			
DM100008	AD457-AD1723	10.78	Lübeck (Hamburg Uni)
DM100003	AD436-AD1968	10.49	Schleswig-Holstein (Hamburg Uni)
SM000002	AD578-AD1293	10.29	Lund NE Skåne Blekinge (Lund University)
dk west	152BC-AD1996	8.65	DK West (Nationalmuseet via Läänelaid)
DM200004	30BC-AD1960	8.32	G Weser (Göttingen Uni)
9M456781	109BC-AD1986	8.09	Jylland/Fyn (Nationalmuseet)
DMML003A	6069BC-AD928	8.00	Moseeg Ost-NDS (Leuschner pers comm)
DM700002	AD12-AD850	7.64	Late Antiquity bridging (Rzepecki et al 2019)
midtjy17	AD536-AD1980	7.43	Mid Jutland (Christensen pers comm)
LUNQSP01	AD621-AD1769	6.42	Lund oak (Bartholin pers comm)
DEhol180	400BC-AD1975	6.40	SW Germany (Hollstein 1980)
PM000005	AD578-AD1010	6.27	PL Wolin (Wazny pers comm)
Site chronologies			
H11CMM01	AD550-AD815	8.85	Haithabu-Siedlung 18 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
0089M001	AD591-AD886	8.42	Szczecin ship 7 timbers (Daly et al 1999)
DE11M004	AD689-AD960	7.33	Borgsumburg Föhr AU2022-78 all 11 timbers (Daly 2022)
H11CLM01	AD637-AD915	7.16	Haithabu-Siedlung 10 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
G3706Z01	AD570-AD661	6.85	Ostbense 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
DE07M002	AD526-AD737	6.41	Reesholm & Kockbarg Schlei Schleswig 17 timbers (Daly 2016b)
7029M001	AD529-AD833	6.23	Nybro/Søvig bæk 44 timbers (Daly 1999 2006)
H11CKM01	AD550-AD887	6.22	Haithabu-Siedlung 75 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)

Table 2. Friedrichsruhe Fpl 2. Result of the correlation between the average curve for the oak samples (PCH515M02) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Brüggstrasse

Two samples are from Brüggstrasse. They are both analysed dendrochronologically, and both are dated. No sapwood is preserved, and the felling date for the trees that these samples come from are estimated at after AD 1243 (515371) and after AD 1230 (515395) respectively (see fig. 1).

The tree-ring curves for the two samples give a correlation between each other of $t = 4.85$, at their dated position. And average of the two, BrüggM01, is 270 years long, and the correlations between this average and tree-ring datasets for northern Europe are shown in table 3. The highest correlation is with a site chronology from Lübeck. A significant correlation also appears with a master chronology from the Netherlands, but this chronology could contain data from timber imported, in the past, to the Low Countries.

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Filename	start year-end year	BrüggsM01 Brüggstrasse AD963-AD1232	site name
Master chronologies			
nlmidden	AD1023-AD1666	7.95	Mid Netherlands (Jansma pers comm)
DM100006start	AD851-AD1293	7.7	Lübeck (Hamburg Uni)
DM100003	AD436-AD1968	5.95	Schleswig-Holstein (Hamburg Uni)
DM200004	30BC-AD1960	5.94	G Weser (Göttingen Uni)
Site chronologies			
H11HEM01	AD863-AD1228	8.39	Lübeck 21 25 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
H11JPM01	AD946-AD1241	7.8	HL Fischstr. 36 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
H1194F02	AD911-AD1234	7.1	Lübeck 73 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
PP103M01	AD1136-AD1335	6.86	PL Gdansk Ratusz 10 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
H1194M02	AD911-AD1234	6.85	Lübeck 70 73 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
G370GZ01	AD970-AD1256	5.96	Ihlow 11 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
P676001M	AD1067-AD1393	5.89	PL Kolobrzeg (Wazny pers comm)
H11BKM01	AD902-AD1070	5.76	HL-90 2 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
GO12QZ01	AD1066-AD1209	5.72	Lübow 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
DD001M000	AD1005-AD1338	5.71	Altenkirchen (Bartholin pers comm)
H200KM02	AD1022-AD1259	5.64	hbg. Grabung 5 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
Chronologies from mobile objects			
Z056m001	AD1065-AD1266	6.47	Egelskärsvraket Finland barrel 4 timbers (Daly 2011a)
Z077M005	AD1053-AD1285	5.63	FPL71 Rostock Ost 7 timbers (Daly 2011b)
Z228M002	AD1030-AD1234	5.54	Wismar Vendorf Fpl30 7 timbers (Daly 2018b)
doel1_all_m2	AD1150-AD1305	5.54	Ship timbers Doel 1 (Haneca & Daly 2014)

Table 3. Brüggstrasse. Result of the correlation between the average curve for the oak samples (BrüggsM01) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Behren Lübchin Fpl 1

Seven samples are from Behren Lübchin Fpl 1 And all these are analysed dendrochronologically. Five samples are dated. None of these have sapwood preserved. Four of the samples agree very well with each other, suggesting that all four are from a single tree (see table 4). This tree was felled after AD 1343 (see fig. 1). Two correlation tables are presented (tables 5 and 6). The sample LRD515470a (table 5) correlates best with a chronology for Lübeck and picks up highly significant correlations also with Kolobrzeg on the southern Baltic coast. The oak that this sample comes from was probably sourced locally.

	LRD515470a	LRD515471a	LRD515472a	LRD515474a	LRD515475a
LRD515470a	*	3.21	2.98	3.57	4.56
LRD515471a	3.21	*	22.51	26.72	30.56
LRD515472a	2.98	22.51	*	27.2	23.84
LRD515474a	3.57	26.72	27.2	*	27.43
LRD515475a	4.56	30.56	23.84	27.43	*

Table 4. Behren Lübchin Fpl 1. Result of the correlation (t -value) of each dated oak tree-ring curve against each other.

The tree LRD5154st1, represented by four samples, is correlating best with datasets from the southern Baltic coast around the Gulf of Gdansk (table 6). While the t -values achieved are not as high as that of the single sample, the dating position is examined visually, and there is, in addition, wide replication of this

dating position. These samples are likely also to be from a tree that was sourced locally to the site.

Filename	start year-end year	LRD515470a Behren Lübchin Fpl 1 AD1101- AD1261	site name
Master chronologies			
DM100008	AD457-AD1723	10.03	Lübeck (Hamburg Uni)
DM100003	AD436-AD1968	8.84	Schleswig-Holstein (Hamburg Uni)
P727001m	AD952-AD1272	8.27	Poland Szczecin (Wazny pers comm)
4M000001	AD1058-AD1350	7.7	Danmark Svendborg (Nationalmuseet)
P671001m	AD980-AD1347	7.52	Poland Elblag (Wazny pers comm)
PM000003	AD1102-AD1431	6.28	Gdansk Pomerania (Wazny pers comm)
DM200006	AD914-AD1873	6.24	Lüneburger Heide (Göttingen Uni)
Site chronologies			
P676001m	AD1084-AD1393	9.57	Poland Kolobrzeg (Wazny pers comm)
PP118M01	AD1112-AD1399	8.28	PL Gdansk various 31 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
DD001M000	AD1005-AD1338	7.58	Altenkirchen (Bartholin pers comm)
0676001S	AD1067-AD1305	7.38	Kolobrzeg 7 timbers (Wazny pers comm)
PM670108	AD725-AD1985	7.32	PL Gdansk (Wazny pers comm)
PP124M01	AD982-AD1356	7.1	PL Elblag 120 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
H11JAM01	AD1118-AD1278	7.04	HL Mengstr.40 8 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
PP125M02	AD913-AD1356	6.97	PL Elblag 79 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP106M01	AD1110-AD1399	6.96	PL Gdansk Parc.6 14 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
Chronologies from mobile objects			
D0132M02	AD1096-AD1336	8.32	Thomas B Thriges staves 7 timbers (Daly 2016a)
Z0051Mall	AD1063-AD1373	7.41	Bøle all 48 timbers (Daly & Nymoen in prep)
doel1_all_m2	AD1150-AD1305	7.07	Ship timbers Doel 1 (Haneca & Daly 2014)
0045M002	AD1109-AD1370	6.84	Vejby skib 18 timbers (Bonde & Jensen 1995)
eqpeeM001	AD1034-AD1286	6.59	Cog Peeter 8 timbers (Läänelaid pers comm)
H0291M01	AD1146-AD1304	6.55	Tracearbejde Aalborg ÅHM7023 barrel 7 timbers (Daly 2021)
Z056m001	AD1065-AD1266	6.47	Egelskärsvraket Finland barrel 4 timbers (Daly 2011a)
Z219M001	AD1103-AD1351	6.25	Vordingborg Båden VIR2812 3 timbers (Daly 2018a, Daly et al 2021)

Table 5. Behren Lübchin Fpl 1. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve for one oak sample (LRD515470a) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Filename	start year-end year	LRD5154st1 same tree AD1200- AD1332	site name
Master chronologies			
PM670108	AD725-AD1985	5.15	PL Gdansk (Wazny pers comm)
P671001m	AD980-AD1347	5.08	Poland Elblag (Wazny pers comm)
3pqepm01	AD996-AD1985	5.06	East Pomerania 205 oaks (Wazny ITRDB)
PM000004	AD996-AD1985	4.92	PL Gdansk Pomerania (Wazny pers comm)
Site chronologies			
PP122M01	AD1006-AD1359	5.71	PL Elblag 114 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
P802001m	AD1209-AD1401	5.59	Poland Krupy (Wazny pers comm)
PP124M01	AD982-AD1356	5.44	PL Elblag 120 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP125M01	AD917-AD1400	5.41	PL Elblag 150 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP126M01	AD1017-AD1393	4.94	PL Elblag 137 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP125M02	AD913-AD1356	4.88	PL Elblag 79 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP114M01	AD1152-AD1447	4.71	PL Gdansk Wole Rogi 18 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
Chronologies from mobile objects			
21214M01	AD1138-AD1321	4.89	Suså barrel (Daly 2001 2007)
0012m002	AD1155-AD1353	4.76	Lille Kregme ship (Eriksen 1992)
Z0051Mall	AD1063-AD1373	4.47	Bøle all 48 timbers (Daly & Nymoen in prep)

Table 6. Behren Lübchin Fpl 1. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve for one tree (LRD5154st1) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Wismar Wendorf OstII Fpl 6

Sixteen samples are from Wismar Wendorf OstII Fpl 6. Four of these contain only 50 tree rings or less and these are not analysed further (see catalogue). Twelve samples are analysed dendrochronologically, and of these seven are dated. Six of the dated samples are from ship planks. These all have only heartwood preserved. Three samples are so similar in their tree-ring pattern (table 7), these might all be from a single tree (same tree 1). Another two samples are also very similar, these might also be from a single tree (same tree 2). The outermost tree ring is on sample 515430 and this is from a tree felled after AD 1376. An average of the six planks, representing three trees, is made (Z331M004). This average is 157 years long. It is dating strongly with tree-ring datasets for the Netherlands (table 8).

The dated sample from a frame has sapwood preserved. The tree-ring curve from the frame is short (67 years), but it is not giving any other strong positions and is giving a *t*-value 5.78 with Lower Saxony (table 9).

The frame is from a tree felled c. AD 1380-95. This indicates the felling date for the trees used to build this ship (see fig. 1).

			Z3310019	Z3310029	Z331003a	Z331008a	Z331009a	Z3310059	Z3310129
average Z331M004	same tree 1	Z3310019	*	18.9	10.8	4.93	4.03	0.51	0.7
		Z3310029	18.9	*	10.6	6.96	4.89	1.75	1.06
		Z331003a	10.8	10.6	*	8.6	4.44	3.55	0.59
	same tree 2	Z331008a	4.93	6.96	8.6	*	4.22	1.99	\
		Z331009a	4.03	4.89	4.44	4.22	*	10.5	\
		Z3310059	0.51	1.75	3.55	1.99	10.5	*	\
		Z3310129	0.7	1.06	0.59	\	\	\	*

Table 7. Wismar Fpl6. Result of the correlation (*t*-value) of each dated oak tree-ring curve against each other.

Filename	start year-end year	Z331M004 Wismar FPL6 planks AD1209- AD1365	site name
Master chronologies			
TWWFMD01	AD1216-AD1660	7.14	NL Twente/Westfalen 51 trees (Dominguez Delmas unpubl)
nlnoor10	AD1041-AD1391	6.7	NL Noord versie 10 (Jansma pers comm)
GBM00010	AD406-AD1594	5.93	Southern England 320 timbers (Sheffield Uni)
nlmidden	AD1023-AD1666	5.59	Mid Netherlands (Jansma 1995)
GBM00006	AD1083-AD1589	5.46	Southern England { Bridge } (Sheffield Uni)
GBM00005	AD413-AD1654	4.29	London Big mean (Sheffield Uni)
nlnoordm	AD1041-AD1346	4.06	Netherlands north (Jansma 1995)
Site chronologies			
se207m01	AD1181-AD1407	5.61	Reading Abbey 14 timbers (Sheffield Uni revised Daly 2007)
Chronologies from mobile objects			
kak00040	AD1250-AD1379	4.04	Kampen kogge ship vn 28 put 3 duik 37 (Delmas pers comm)

Table 8. Wismar FPL6 planks. Result of the correlation between the average curve for the oak plank samples (Z331M004) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

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Filename	start year-end year	Z3310129 Wismar FPL6 frame AD1313- AD1379	site name
Master chronologies			
DM200005	AD915-AD1873	5.78	Niedersachsen Nord (Göttingen Uni)
DM200006	AD914-AD1873	5.31	Lüneburger Heide (Göttingen Uni)
SM000005	AD1274-AD1974	5.11	Skåne Blekinge (Lund University)
Site chronologies			
G3708Z01	AD1302-AD1520	4.97	Hankhausen 3 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
G350PZ01	AD967-AD1381	4.93	Truhen 46 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
G1201Z02	AD1318-AD1536	4.87	Wedel 21 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
G311RZ01	AD1320-AD1548	4.47	Helmarshausen 12 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
G3510Z02	AD1291-AD1451	4.34	Lüneburg 9 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
Chronologies from mobile objects			
Z0051M04	AD1176-AD1367	4.05	Bøle group 4 r-planks 1 t-plank 4 timbers (Daly & Nymoer in prep)

Table 9. Wismar FPL6. Result of the correlation between the average curve for the oak frame sample (Z3310129) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Wismar OstII Fpl 10

Sixteen samples are from Wismar OstII Fpl 10. Seven of these contain less than 65 rings, and these are not analysed further (see catalogue). Of the nine samples analysed dendrochronologically six are dated (one from a plank and five from frames).

The plank sample has only heartwood and is from a tree felled after AD 1530. The five dated frames form a group, and one of these has probable heartwood/sapwood boundary preserved. This sample is from a tree felled probably c. AD 1535-50, and this dating would agree with the *termini post quem* of the other frames in this group (see fig. 1).

The dated samples match each other as shown in table 10 (in orange). An average Z332M003 is made, which is 117 years long. This is correlating very significantly with tree-ring datasets for Lübeck (table 11).

	Z332002a	Z3320049	Z332007a	Z3320109	Z332005a	Z332006a	Z332003a
Z332002a fpl32	*	-	-	\	0.52	\	-
average Z332M003 frame Z3320049	-	*	5.86	3.92	2.78	4.01	2.29
frame Z332007a	-	5.86	*	5.87	3.83	4.06	4.21
frame Z3320109	\	3.92	5.87	*	5.85	4.05	2.95
frame Z332005a	0.52	2.78	3.83	5.85	*	6.87	3.25
frame Z332006a	\	4.01	4.06	4.05	6.87	*	4.87
515448 plank Z332003a	-	2.29	4.21	2.95	3.25	4.87	*

Table 10 Wismar Fpl10 and fpl32. Result of the correlation (*t*-value) of each dated oak tree-ring curve against each other.

Filename	start year-end year	Z332M003 Wismar OstII Fpl 10 AD1409- AD1525	site name
Master chronologies			
DM100008	AD457-AD1723	7.65	Lübeck (Hamburg Uni)
DM100003	AD436-AD1968	6.85	Schleswig-Holstein (Hamburg Uni)
DM100007	AD1080-AD1967	6.8	Hamburg (Hamburg Uni)
DM200005	AD915-AD1873	6.56	Niedersachsen Nord (Göttingen Uni)
Site chronologies			
H11H6M01	AD1391-AD1544	7.38	HL Gr.Petersgrube 18 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
H12BVM01	AD1454-AD1557	7.14	Hohenhorst Wildkoppe 2 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
H11KLM01	AD1385-AD1589	6.78	HL Mengstr. 44 18 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
H115CM01	AD1452-AD1674	6.64	Preetz Markt 24 9 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
H11HJM01	AD1423-AD1547	6.48	HL Hundestr. 71 12 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
H11HHM01	AD1379-AD1531	6.29	HL Langer Lohberg 47 14 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
H11IWM01	AD1389-AD1571	6.26	HL Gr.Petersgrube 29 15 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
H1178M01	AD1397-AD1624	6.18	Preetz Thiemenhaus + Klosterhof 19 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
G1201Z02	AD1318-AD1536	6.17	Wedel 21 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
H11ISM01	AD1389-AD1563	6.14	HL Alfstrasse 38 9 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
H1177M01	AD1424-AD1585	6.07	Preetz Klosterh. 19. 8 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
H11K2M02	AD1399-AD1549	6.05	HL Koenigstr 11 13 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
Chronologies from mobile objects			
Z1813M01	AD1473-AD1565	7.37	Kirkestræde 6 A37 Tønde2 latrine 4 timbers (Daly & Nielsen 2016)
Z093M001	AD1420-AD1614	7.05	Vasa barrels 7 timbers (Daly 2013)
005400m1	AD1368-AD1592	6.33	Bredfjed skib all samples (Daly 2007)

Table 11. Wismar OstII Fpl 10. Result of the correlation between the average curve for the oak samples (Z332M003) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Filename	start year-end year	Z332002a Wismar OstII fpl32 AD1502- AD1634	site name
Master chronologies			
DM100001	AD1310-AD1968	5.61	Schleswig-Holstein (Hamburg Uni)
DM100007	AD1080-AD1967	5.6	Hamburg (Hamburg Uni)
DM200004	30BC-AD1960	5.37	G Weser (Göttingen Uni)
E_German	AD1343-AD1968	5.21	East Germany Climate project sites 339 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Site chronologies			
G314HZ01	AD1545-AD1784	6.6	Hann.Münden 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
H128ZM01	AD1508-AD1625	6.34	Uetersen Lohe 25. 3 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
G3159Z01	AD1493-AD1669	5.86	Hann.Münden 3 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
G311FZ01	AD1530-AD1684	5.76	Bodenwerder 5 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
G311OZ01	AD1521-AD1638	5.39	Lippoldsberg 9 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
G316OZ01	AD1504-AD1740	5.24	Dransfeld 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
HO11ZM01	AD1441-AD1678	5.23	Gadeb. Mühlenstr. 15 3 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
HO34MM01	AD1562-AD1735	5.23	Boitzenb. Klingbergs 10 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
G3205Z03	AD1481-AD1651	5.21	Walkenried 5 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
Chronologies from mobile objects			
F0041M01	AD1433-AD1652	7.39	Viborg Skt Pederstræde barrel base 3 timbers (Daly 2007)
NormBay_T3	AD1415-AD1623	5.1	NormBay_T3 3 timbers (Nayling pers comm)

Table 12. Wismar OstII fpl32. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve for one oak sample (Z332002a) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Fpl 32

One frame labelled Wismar OstII fpl(32)10 515502 (Z332002a) does not match the Fpl10 group (see table 10). It has sapwood preserved and the tree that it comes from was felled c. AD 1635-47 (fig. 1). On its label is written "Fpl (32)10" so there might have been doubt as to what find this belongs. It is probable that this sample is from a frame from a different ship. The correlations that it achieves when compared to tree-ring datasets for oak for Northern Europe are shown in table 12. It is correlating with master chronologies from Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg, and with site chronologies from the Hamburg hinterland.

Poel Timendorf Fpl 11

One sample is from Poel Timendorf Fpl 11. This sample is from the Poel 11 ship, dated previously to AD 1773 or shortly after (Daly & Belasus 2015). This sample is pine and it is dated. It is from a tree felled after AD 1699 (indicated with orange shading in fig. 1). The sample correlates with the combined chronology for the Poel and Hiddensee ships with a t -value of $t = 6.25$.

Rostock Grubenstrasse Fpl 411

Eight samples are from Rostock Grubenstrasse Fpl 411. Three of these contain less than 55 tree rings and are not analysed further. Of the five samples analysed dendrochronologically, none are dated.

Alt Strassow Fpl 8

Six samples are from Alt Strassow Fpl 8. Four contain less than 65 tree rings and these four were not analysed further. Two samples that were analysed dendrochronologically could not be dated (see catalogue). They also contain too few tree rings for successful dating.

Loitz Fpl 7

One sample is from Loitz Fpl 7. It was analysed dendrochronologically, but could not be dated (see catalogue).

Methodology

Measuring and analysis of the material is carried out using the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) in which the calculation of the t -value (" t -test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is embedded. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are consulted.

For estimating the felling date of the oak trees that are dated, a sapwood average of c. 10-25 sapwood rings is used. This is an approximate combination of a statistic for North Germany (c. 20 sapwood years (-5+10) (Hollstein 1980)) and for Northern Poland (c. 15 years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990)).

Fig. 1. Diverse samples from Mecklenburg-Vorpommern. The chronological position of the dated samples.

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**When quoting these results please add the following:
in publication bibliography/literature lists:**

Daly, Aoife, 2023. Dendrochronological analysis of diverse timbers from Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, Germany. *Dendro.dk report* 2023:45, Copenhagen.

In blogs and social media: *dendro.dk report* 2023:45.

Catalogue

Friedrichsruhe

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	genus	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
samples dated												
PCH515440a	PCH Friedrichsruhe 515440 fpl2	163	AD640	AD802	G	0	N	R	N	QUSP	1.70	after AD812
PCH5154449	PCH Friedrichsruhe 515444 fpl2	229	AD569	AD797	G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	0.99	after AD808
PCH515521a	PCH Friedrichsruhe 159 515521 fpl2	247	AD568	AD814	G	0	N	R	N	QUSP	1.01	after AD824
PCH5155239	PCH Friedrichsruhe 515523 fpl2 97	218	AD611	AD828	G	0	N	O	H1	QUSP	0.76	after AD839
PCH5155249	PCH Friedrichsruhe 515524 fpl2 148	139	AD691	AD829	G	0	N	O	H1	QUSP	0.84	after AD840
PCH5155259	PCH Friedrichsruhe 98 515525 fpl2	194	AD652	AD845	G	5	N	O	S1	QUSP	0.75	AD850-65
PCH5155269	PCH Friedrichsruhe 99 515526 fpl2	194	AD648	AD841	G	0	N	Q	H1	QUSP	0.75	after AD852
samples undated												
PCH5154419	PCH Friedrichsruhe 515441 fpl2 141	111			G	0	N	O	N	QUSP	1.58	undated
samples not measured												
	PCH Friedrichsruhe 515527 fpl2 160	40								QUSP		
	PCH Friedrichsruhe 515528 fpl2 138	30								QUSP		
	PCH Friedrichsruhe 515529 fpl2 156	60								QUSP		knotty
	PCH Friedrichsruhe 515522 fpl2 142	41								QUSP		
averages												
PCH515M01	PCH Friedrichsruhe 99 fpl2 5 timbers	278	AD568	AD845						QUSP	1.03	
PCH515M02	PCH Friedrichsruhe fpl2 7 timbers	278	AD568	AD845						QUSP	0.96	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus</i> sp., oak. PISY = <i>Pinus</i> sp., pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix</i> sp., spruce/larch. ABAL = <i>Abies</i> sp., fir. FASY = <i>Fagus</i> sp., beech												
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.					14 April 2023							

14 April 2023

Other

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	genus	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
samples dated												
HGW515371a	Brüggstrasse HGW515371 plank	259	AD974	AD1232	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	0.86	after AD1243
HGW5153959	Brüggstrasse HGW515395 plank	257	AD963	AD1219	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	0.95	after AD1230
DE10001a	Poel Timendorf fpl11 planke 515396	76	AD1623	AD1698	F	0	N	T	H1	PISY	1.81	after AD1699
samples undated												
DBR5154659	DBR Alt Strassow Fpl8 515465	64			V	22	N	T	S1	QUSP	1.90	undated
DBR5154689	DBR Alt Strassow Fpl8 515468	74			F	22	X	T	N	QUSP	1.87	undated
DM5154139	DM Loitz fpl7 DM515413 C-beam	146			G	15	N	O	S1	QUSP	1.26	undated
samples not measured												
	DBR Alt Strassow Fpl8 515464	40								QUSP		
	DBR Alt Strassow Fpl8 515466	40								QUSP		
	DBR Alt Strassow Fpl8 515467	55								QUSP		
	DBR Alt Strassow Fpl8 515469	63								QUSP		
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus</i> sp., oak. PISY = <i>Pinus</i> sp., pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix</i> sp., spruce/larch. ABAL = <i>Abies</i> sp., fir. FASY = <i>Fagus</i> sp., beech												
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.				14 April 2023								

Behren Lübchin

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	genus	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
samples dated												
LRD515470a	Behren Lübchin LRD fpl1 515470 plank	161	AD1101	AD1261	G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	1.42	after AD1272
LRD515471a	Behren Lübchin LRD fpl1 515471 plank	133	AD1200	AD1332	G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	1.55	after AD1343
LRD515472a	Behren Lübchin LRD fpl1 515472 plank	100	AD1231	AD1330	G	0	N	R	N	QUSP	1.67	after AD1343
LRD515474a	Behren Lübchin LRD fpl1 515474 plank	114	AD1216	AD1329	G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	1.77	after AD1343
LRD515475a	Behren Lübchin LRD fpl1 515475 plank	113	AD1213	AD1325	G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	1.64	after AD1343
samples undated												
LRD515473a	Behren Lübchin LRD fpl1 515473 plank	56			G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	2.60	undated
LRD515476a	Behren Lübchin LRD fpl1 515476 8th	125			G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	1.14	undated
same tree												
LRD5154st1	Behren Lübchin LRD fpl1 515471 2 4 5 same tree	133	AD1200	AD1332	G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	1.77	after AD1343
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus</i> sp., oak. PISY = <i>Pinus</i> sp., pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix</i> sp., spruce/larch. ABAL = <i>Abies</i> sp., fir. FASY = <i>Fagus</i> sp., beech												
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.				14 April 2023								

14 April 2023

Wismar Wendorf OstII Fpl 6

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	genus	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
samples dated												
Z3310019	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 plank 2 00000515430	82	AD1284	AD1365	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	1.84	after AD1376
Z3310029	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 plank 9 515433	81	AD1260	AD1340	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	1.97	after AD1351
Z331003a	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 plank 2 515439	127	AD1209	AD1335	V	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	2.45	after AD1346
Z3310059	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 plank 4 515435	89	AD1212	AD1300	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	1.22	after AD1311
Z331008a	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 plank 15 515417	89	AD1225	AD1313	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	2.24	after AD1324
Z331009a	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 plank 4 515434	87	AD1222	AD1308	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	1.35	after AD1319
Z3310129	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 frame 22 515419	67	AD1313	AD1379	C	9	N	H	N	QUSP	1.34	AD1380-95
samples undated												
Z3310049	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 plank 1 515431	109			G	0	N	T	N	QUSP	1.96	undated
Z331006a	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 plank 8 515436	83			G	0	N	T	H9	QUSP	1.65	undated
Z3310079	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 plank 6 515438	68			G	0	N	T	N	QUSP	1.89	undated
Z3310109	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 keel1 515429	65			C	0	N	T	N	QUSP	2.48	undated
Z3310119	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 plank 6 515432	92			G	0	N	T	N	QUSP	1.48	undated
samples not measured												
	Wismar OstII fpl6 515418	20								QUSP		
	Wismar OstII fpl6 515416	55								QUSP		
	Wismar OstII fpl6 515415	50								QUSP		
	Wismar OstII fpl6 515437	50								QUSP		
same tree												
Z331004&7 st	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 plank 1&6	109			G	0	N	T	N	QUSP	1.95	undated
averages												
Z331M001	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 6 timbers	157	AD1209	AD1365						QUSP	1.85	
Z331M002	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 3 timbers	157	AD1209	AD1365						QUSP	2.41	
Z331M003	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl6 2 timbers	133								QUSP	1.72	undated
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus</i> sp., oak. PISY = <i>Pinus</i> sp., pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix</i> sp., spruce/larch. ABAL = <i>Abies</i> sp., fir. FASY = <i>Fagus</i> sp., beech												
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.				14 April 2023								

Wismar OstII Fpl 10

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	genus	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
samples dated												
Z332002a	Wismar OstII fpl(32)10 515502 frame	133	AD1502	AD1634	F	12	N	O	S1	QUSP	1.29	AD1635-47
Z332003a	Wismar OstII fpl10 515448 plank	62	AD1458	AD1519	G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	3.33	after AD1530
Z3320049	Wismar OstII fpl10 515361 frame	92	AD1427	AD1518	C	0	N	S	H1	QUSP	1.30	after AD1529
Z332005a	Wismar OstII fpl10 515364 frame	117	AD1409	AD1525	C	?	N	O	N	QUSP	1.05	AD1535-50?
Z332006a	Wismar OstII fpl10 515372 frame	105	AD1411	AD1515	F	0	N	O	H1	QUSP	1.25	after AD1526
Z332007a	Wismar OstII fpl10 515363 frame	109	AD1417	AD1525	V	0	N	O	H1	QUSP	1.52	after AD1536
Z3320109	Wismar Wendorf OstII fpl10 frame 515462	77	AD1412	AD1488	C	0	N	S	N	QUSP	1.45	after AD1498
samples undated												
Z332001a	Wismar OstII fpl10 515447	95			G	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	2.19	undated
Z3320089	Wismar OstII fpl10 515461 timber	165			F	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	0.83	undated
Z332009a	Wismar OstII fpl10 515503 construction element	86			F	17	N	T	S1	QUSP	1.37	undated
samples not measured												
	Wismar OstII fpl10 515362	43								QUSP		
	Wismar OstII fpl10 515366	25								QUSP		
	Wismar OstII fpl10 515367	40								QUSP		
	Wismar OstII fpl10 515368	40								QUSP		
	Wismar OstII fpl10 515394	63								QUSP		
	Wismar OstII fpl10 515501	20								Alder?		
	Wismar OstII fpl10 515504	35								QUSP		
averages												
Z332M001	Wismar OstII fpl10 frames 2 timbers	117	AD1409	AD1525						QUSP	1.13	
Z332M002	Wismar OstII fpl10 frames 2 timbers	109	AD1417	AD1525						QUSP	1.47	
Z332M003	Wismar OstII fpl10 6 timbers	117	AD1409	AD1525						QUSP	1.51	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 - 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus</i> sp., oak. PISY = <i>Pinus</i> sp., pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix</i> sp., spruce/larch. ABAL = <i>Abies</i> sp., fir. FASY = <i>Fagus</i> sp., beech												
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.						14 April 2023						

14 April 2023

Rostock Grubenstrasse

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	genus	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
samples undated												
HRO515463a	HRO Rostock fpl411 515463	118			C	0	N	O	H1	QUSP	1.75	not dated
HRO5154069	Rostock Grubenstrasse 515406 fpl411	87			C	6	N	S	S1	QUSP	0.70	undated
HRO515407a	Rostock Grubenstrasse 515407 fpl411	140			C	0	N	S	N	QUSP	0.48	undated
HRO5154099	Rostock Grubenstrasse 515409 fpl411	97			G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	1.23	undated
HRO515410a	Rostock Grubenstrasse 214 515410 fpl411	103			G	0	N	R	H1	QUSP	1.34	undated
samples not measured												
	Rostock Grubenstrasse 515408 fpl411	52								QUSP		
	Rostock Grubenstrasse 515412 fpl411	52								QUSP		
	Rostock Grubenstrasse 515411 fpl411	55								QUSP		
averages												
HROM001	Rostock Grubenstrasse 2 timbers	103								QUSP	1.29	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus</i> sp., oak. PISY = <i>Pinus</i> sp., pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix</i> sp., spruce/larch. ABAL = <i>Abies</i> sp., fir. FASY = <i>Fagus</i> sp., beech												
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.						14 April 2023						